

IMPACT OF OIL PRICES SHOCK ON MACRO-ECONOMIC INDICATORS: A CASE STUDY OF PAKISTAN

ASIFA BEGAM ABBASI

Lecturer, Government Girls Degree College Larkana. Email: abbasi.asifa@yahoo.com

Dr. ERUM KHUSHNOOD ZAHID SHAIKH

Professor, Abida Taherani Sindh Dvelopment Study Center (ATSDSC), University of Sindh, Jamshoro. Email: erum@usindh.edu.pk

Abstract

In this study we examined the impact of oil price shocks on macro- economic indicators (i.e., Gross Domestic Product, inflation, investment, money supply & exchange rate) by applying the Vector Autoregressive Model and using quarterly data (i.e. from 1961q1- 2022q1). Results of Vector Autoregressive model suggested that the oil price has significant influence on economic conditions in a country. Moreover, oil price has shown the negative effect on GDP and investment, while as oil price has positively affected on inflation. Furthermore, granger causality test shows the bidirectional relationship among the oil price and GDP, oil price and investment other variables are uni-variate. Impulse response and factor variance decomposition has showed the oil price has significant impact on major economic indicators of Pakistan. This study also retained some limitations in the context of Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION

Crude oil is one of the most important sources of energy in today's economy that is required for smooth running of all sectors of economy and to achieve economic development of a country (Månsson, 2014). Variations in demand and supply of oil lead to the shocks in oil price (Nasir et al., 2019).

Economists agreed on the oil price shocks are dampened the economic activities, which increased the inflation and decreased of Gross Domestic Product (Bruno & Sachs, 1982; Rasche & Tatom, 1981).

Various previous studies such as Hamilton (1983), Lardic (2006), Mohammed & Alom, (2016), Ahad & Anwer, (2021), Chen et al., (2020) and Mantai & Alom, (2016) confirmed the significantly positive as well as negative impact of oil price shocks on the economic stability of a country.

Pakistan is developing country of the world its weak and unstable economy highly depends on imported crude oil (OECD, 2011 & World Bank, 2023). Figure 1 presents the world's three oil price shocks, first oil price shock was observed in 1973, this shock escalated the oil price 4.15 to 9.07 dollar.

Second oil price was observed in 1979 and oil price raised 12.46 -35.24 dollar. Third shock was seen in the 2007- 2008 it surged the oil price 145 dollar the main reason of oil shock was oil supply; the supply was restricted by the oil exporting countries (US Energy Information Administration, 2018).

Figure 1: World Average Annual Crude Oil Prices n = 62 years

Source: World Bank, 2023

The Figure - 2 presents, trends of production and consumption of crude oil in the world. Presented trends indicative that the consumption of crude oil is more than production in majority of years. The world consumption surged to 0.6% to 1.3% and millions per barrel is 73985.51 to 77067.25 in 2005 to 2008. In 2007-2008 most countries faced financial crises due to shortage of production (US Energy Information Administration, 2018).

Figure 2: World Production & Consumption of Crude Oil in Millions Per Barrel n=42

Source: US Energy Information Administration,2018 & World Bank (2023)

Pakistan is the fifth populous country of the world; therefore, the need of energy is day by day increasing. Major demand of energy is fulfilled with crude oil, crude oil is used to run the various sectors of economy whenever oil price raise it effected whole economy and its macro variables moves up and down due to oil price fluctuation (Economic Survey of Pakistan, 2017-2018). Oil price remained the problem for Pakistan economy, oil price creates huge out flow of money from country, from 2007 to 2008 financial crises have evident, Pakistan economy responds to the fluctuation of oil prices these shocks are left the adverse effect on Pakistan economy. Oil price shocks are main reason to increase the inflation in Pakistan, which was about 20.8% in 2008- 2009 that was created the inflationary pressure on overall economy (World Bank Report, 2008). The purpose of this research was to examine the impact of oil price shocks on macroeconomic variables in Pakistan's economy.

Several studies such as Mohammed & Alom, (2016), Ahad & Anwer, (2021), Chen et al., (2020) and Mantai & Alom, (2016) have been conducted on oil price shocks and macroeconomics variables However, these studies covering inadequate data or annual data While this study based on quarterly data covering large sample size specifically in the context of Pakistan at thesis level.

In Pakistan majority of studies focused on the relationship between oil price and macro-economic variables of the economy. Which is not sufficient to identify the impact of sudden shocks in economy. Majority of past studies do not come with the satisfactory conclusions about impact of oil price shock on other macroeconomic variables. In this regard this study will analyze the dynamic impact of oil price with special focus on Pakistan. Most of international studies used the industrial production index as proxy of gross domestic product but due to unavailability of required data of industrial production index in Pakistan, this study used Gross Domestic Product (growth rate) rather than industrial production index. In addition, at Pakistan level, other studies covering the time period from 1990 to 2014. While this study based on quarterly data covering the period from 1961Q1 to 2017Q1.

The study contributes to minimize the macroeconomic effects of oil price shocks and to achieve economic growth stability in several ways. First, this study investigates the relationship between key macro-economic variables and dynamic impact of oil price shocks with special focuses on oil importing countries which according to my best knowledge is very few studies are observed on Pakistan. Second, this study provides fresh evidence on identifying the macroeconomic effects of oil price shock on Pakistan's economy. Third, this study applies the latest empirical methodology, VAR, and provides new empirical evidence about the dynamic impact of oil price shocks on macroeconomic variables in Pakistan's economy.

The study covers all wider sample quarterly data that is total 245 observations (time period, 1961Q1-2022 Q1) thus, the study is one of the comprehensive research work which provides much-needed insight about the movement of key macro-economic variable resulting of oil price shocks in the oil importing economy, Pakistan.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Oil is the one of essential commodity which would be reason of prosperity and stagnation of economy. According to Hamilton,1983 increment in oil prices negatively affect macroeconomic activities of oil-importing countries through the supply-side and demand-side channels (Hamilton, 1983, Tariq, M., & Saleem, M., 2023). The role of oil price is important for both importer and exporter countries. Oil price has positive impact on the economy of exporter countries such as escalation of oil prices are cause of foreign exchange inflow, upsurge of growth rate and decrease of inflation (Roeger, 2005, Prasad et al., 2007, Sek et al., 2015). On other side, negative impact of oil price often observed on oil importer countries (Huntington, 1998, Lardic, 2006, Hrushikesh Mallik, 2009, Dave & Aye, 2015, Castillo et al., 2020, Khan & ahmed, 2010). The oil-importing countries are the most anxious owing to their high dependency on imported oil. Oil price has negatively affected the gross domestic product and increase the inflation within oil importing countries, whenever oil price surge occurred it reduced the gross domestic product (growth rate) and increase the inflation in the economy. Bhattacharya & Bhattacharyya (2001), explained the transmission system of a rise of oil price is cause of increase the prices of commodities and output. This study used the Vector Autoregressive Model; variables are (i.e., oil price, output, inflation, broad money). The transmission mechanism supports the bidirectional relation between oil and other variables except inflation. This bidirectional causal relation is suitable for policy analysts. The impulse response showed the 20% variation in inflation, this oil shock increased the inflation 1.3%. Oil price shock is also a reason to decline the gross domestic product that is 2.1 % . Khan and Ahmad (2011) use monthly data spanning from 1990 to 2011 to examine the effect of food and oil prices shock on domestic output, inflation, interest rate and exchange rate in Pakistan. The result from SVAR and GIR shows that oil price shocks transmit through interest rate and exchange rate channels while other variables as used in the study are not responsive. Mark (1996) explained the role of oil price in economy with the help of Vector Autoregressive methodology. Structural breaks found in the USA in 1973; it deteriorated the economy. Researcher further explained that oil price was considered to be an exogenous variable from 1973. Therefore, the Granger causality test shows two-way relationships, moreover the oil price Granger causes on the GDP and unemployment. Moreover, results indicate, oil price is diminishing real GDP and unemployment. K. Lee et al., (1995) diagnose the causality in oil price and economy from 1992. The earlier era showed the positive correlation between Gross National Product (GNP) and oil price from 1986-1987 and 1990 to 1992. After those periods, vice versa trend observed due to the escalation of oil price. It has given the picture to explore further relation of gross national product and oil price. Gross national product used as dependent variable in Vector Autoregressive model, the study found that all variables are significant from 1948 -1986. Eyden et al., (2019), Growth rate of countries are taken from 1870 to 2013. Growth rate of some countries are 2.95%. While some countries showed marginally high growth rate (i.e., Japan 4.34%, Canada 3.68%, Netherland 3.64%). Overall, the economic growth of countries is significant at 1%, As per estimated result, one unit rise of oil price cause to decrease the growth rate. It is evidence of oil price uncertainty; these fluctuations are the

cause of reducing the growth rate 2.95- 2.85% and cross-sectional dependence 5%. Investment and growth rate play a positive role in the economic performance of a country. Chen et al., (2020), selected a VEC technique to examine the variation in the economic condition of China and response of oil price fluctuations. This study got the data from 1999 to 2008 monthly. The study discovered the crude price negatively impacted on output, money supply, although CPI has a positive effect. Hem & kamal (2015), assesses repercussions of the oil price shocks on inflation, GDP, inflation, exchange rate. The ASEAN countries are taken for this study and Structural Vector Autoregressive Model applied. This research used quarterly data from 1970-2010. ASEAN countries are the fastest growing countries in Asia. Therefore, energy requirements are rapidly increasing due to fastest industrialization. ASEAN controlled the 40% share of oil and gas reserves. The co-integration test revealed the variables are co-integrated the long run. The study shows the oil price shock is not an obstacle in economic growth in ASEAN countries. Impulse response indicated the oil price shock has been observed in 5th -6th quarter. Moreover, Variance of Decomposition does not show any significant impact on macro variables. Cologni & Manera, (2008), the study reveals the shock of oil price on monetary variables. G7 countries are included and data carried from 1970-2003, Structural co-integrated Vector Autoregressive Model is used to find the results. Variables are used in this study such as interest rate, M1, CPI, Real GDP, exchange rate. The co-integration test showed the long run relationship among all countries except Canada. In this study results clearly showed the oil price has a significant influence on inflation. Inflation shock is the cause of fluctuation of interest rate; this shock is transmitted in the economy. Abbritti et al., (2020), enquires the effect the price of oil shocks on macro factors of the American economy and data is taken from 1974 - 2016 monthly. This study data is covering two world oil shocks which are observed in different time periods. Those shocks are: Iranian revolution 1978 to 1979, Iran Iraq war of 1980, Gulf crises 1980 and financial crises of 2007 to 2008. The study employed industrial production, real interest rate, unemployed rate, credit spreads variables. In the start period, interest rate initially declines due oil price inflationary shock and credit spread rise. It dampens the demand for capital because investors are afraid of being bankrupt. After one year, prices moved toward the original level which reduced the inflationary pressure on the economy. Interest rate and credit spread are converted significantly positively. As per unemployment, response is slow and it rarely impacts on unemployment. Sadiq, M., & Zafar, S., (2022) & Gong et al., (2020), Bedrock of this study is methodology, this study is applied the novel GARCH-MIDAS model. The study showed the macroeconomic variables volatility are affected on crude price fluctuations. The results found the long-term relation and all the parameters are significant. It showed the strongly significant and some other interesting characteristics are summation of alpha and beta 0.1972, and 0.9185-0.9261 respectively. The significance is less than 1 which shows low volatility of oil price. Furthermore, macro variables suggested that inflation, import and export growth are negatively affected the volatility in long term. On the other hand, the exchange rate is contrary to the previous two variable results (positive impact on exchange rate). Further Short run interest rate is significantly positive to the oil price. Jin-Yu Chen, Xue-Hong Zhu, Mei-Rui Zhong (2019),

applied Time Varying Parameter Structural Vector Autoregressive with stochastic volatility TVP-SVAR-SV model to capture the structural change and time varying correlation of oil price and output. This study comprises of two objectives: the first one is dynamic impact of oil market shocks on the output, second one to capture structural changes in financial crises. Furthermore, oil supply shocks had a positive influence on the oil industry output from 2006 to 2007 but it turned negative in 2008. The upstream demand of oil shocks responded negatively in 2008 to 2009. Moreover, the oil demand shock has a positive effect on output then turned negative in 2010. Speculative demand showed a positive trend. The study focused on the connection between the price of oil and trade balance during the year of 1991Q1-2015Q2. It analyses asymmetric impact on BRICS along with the variable trade balance for structural break. This study confirms the relationship among oil price, trade balance, and wholesale price positively. The study depicted the positive significant association with trade deficit for China, India, and South Africa. But Brazil is in a trade surplus due to an increase in wholesale price. Trade deficit found for India and Russia in the long run and short run. The study content has been beneficial for policy makers and analysts due to the relation of oil price and trade balance. The nonlinear distributed lag (NRDL) model used and co-integration test found the short run and long run asymmetric relation. The Wald test confirmed the oil price was significant at 1 to 2% level with the economic activities and rejected the long run symmetry with all countries except China. Furthermore, relation of oil price, trade balance, whole sale and economic activity is long run (Muhammad Ahad & Anwer, 2021 & Nawab et al. 2023).

To sum up, since the first oil shock in 1973/74, much research has been undertaken into the oil price–macro economy nexus. These studies have reached different conclusions over time. However, it is confirmed from literature review that oil price has great effect on economic activities. On the bases of review literature, it is concluded that oil price has significant impact on macro-economic variables such as inflation, gross domestic product, exchange rate however, the money supply does not affect directly, oil price impact on money supply observed through monetary policy implementation. Furthermore, most of the previous studies based on panel data. whereas time series analysis is limited. Oil price has significant impact of economy of Pakistan; Pakistan economy is sensitive towards increasing of oil price. Oil price is major concern for developing and oil importing countries like Pakistan.

METHODOLOGY

In this paper we used the vector auto-regressive methodology because entire variables are measured as endogenous, there is no need to worry about which one is exogenous or the other is endogenous. It is used separately in each equation and the forecast method is better than the simultaneous equation model (Gujrati, 2012). Sims (1980) explained the Vector Autoregressive model is served for three functions: (1) forecast the time series (2) develop the economic model (3) to develop the alternative policy (Christiano, 2012). The VAR model is one of the useful approaches to deal with oil price shock and economic variables. The VAR model has many advantages like examining the structural shock for using Impulse Response Function and Variance Decomposition. The ultimate object of

this study is identified accurate short term forecasts and estimate and remove the insignificant parameters from the model. The VAR model has been used in this study which shows the multivariate Generalization of an Autoregressive process (Hafer & Sheehan, 1989).

The Vector Autoregressive model is used to express the linear inter-dependencies in the time series. All the variables behave as symmetrically and each equation in the model has its own lag. The model given is extracted from Fiza Qureshi, 2017.

$$Y_t = \alpha_0 + \sum \beta_1 Y_{t-1} + \sum \beta_2 X_{t-1} + e \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

This equation used by Walter Enders in his fourth edition, in this equation where

$Y_t = n \times 1$ which indicates the vector consists on n variables in the VAR, $\alpha_0 = (n \times 1)$ is the vector of intercept, $A_i = (n \times n)$ metrics of coefficient $e = n \times 1$ vector of error term.

$$X_t = \alpha_t + \sum \beta_3 oilp_{t-1} + \sum \beta_4 X_{t-1} + e \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

X

Whereas shows the vector of macro variables (i-e GDP, Inflation, Investment, Exchange Rate, m2).

GDP stands for Gross domestic Product (growth rate), m2 is money supply, e stands for error term.

$$\begin{aligned} \ln op_t = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln op_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln op_{t-k} + \beta_1 \ln gdp_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln gdp_{t-k} + \\ & \beta_1 \ln inf_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln inf_{t-k} + \beta_1 \ln inv_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln inv_{t-k} + \beta_1 \ln exc_{t-1} + \dots + \\ & \beta_k \ln exc_{t-k} + \beta_1 \ln m2_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln m2_{t-k} + e \end{aligned} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

The equation three indicates the impact of oil price on macro-economic variables (i,e gross domestic product, money Supply, inflation, investment, Exchange Rate) and on itself

$$\begin{aligned} \ln gdp_t = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln gdp_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln gdp_{t-k} + \beta_1 \ln op_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln op_{t-k} + \\ & \beta_1 \ln inf_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln inf_{t-k} + \beta_1 \ln inv_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln inv_{t-k} + \beta_1 \ln exc_{t-1} + \dots + \\ & \beta_k \ln exc_{t-k} + \beta_1 \ln m2_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln m2_{t-k} + e^1 \end{aligned} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

The equation four indicates the impact of gross Domestic product on oil price macro-economic variables (i,e gross domestic production, money Supply, inflation, investment, Exchange Rate) and on itself.

$$\begin{aligned} \ln inf_t = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln inf_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln inf_{t-k} + \beta_1 \ln gdp_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln gdp_{t-k} + \\ & \beta_1 \ln op_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln op_{t-k} + \beta_1 \ln inv_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln inv_{t-k} + \beta_1 \ln exc_{t-1} + \dots + \\ & \beta_k \ln exc_{t-k} + \beta_1 \ln m2_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln m2_{t-k} + e \end{aligned} \quad \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

The equation five indicates the impact of inflation on oil price macro-economic variables (i.e gross domestic production, money Supply, inflation, investment, Exchange Rate) and on itself

$$\begin{aligned} \ln inv_t = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln inv_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln inv_{t-k} + \beta_1 \ln gdp_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln gdp_{t-k} + \\ & \beta_1 \ln inf_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln inf_{t-k} + \beta_1 \ln op_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln op_{t-k} + \beta_1 \ln exc_{t-1} + \dots + \\ & \beta_k \ln exc_{t-k} + \beta_1 \ln m2_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln m2_{t-k} + e \end{aligned} \quad \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

The equation six shows the investment has an impact on itself oil price, economic variables.

$$\begin{aligned} \ln exc_t = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln exc + \dots + \beta_k \ln exc_{t-k} + \beta_1 \ln gdp_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln gdp_{t-k} + \\ & \beta_1 \ln inf_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln inf_{t-k} + \beta_1 \ln inv_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln inv_{t-k} + \beta_1 \ln op_{t-1} + \dots + \\ & \beta_k \ln op_{t-k} + \beta_1 \ln m2_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln m2_{t-k} + e \dots\dots\dots (7) \end{aligned}$$

The equation indicates the exchange rate has an impact on the macro-economic variables, oil Price also influence on itself.

$$\begin{aligned} \ln m2_t = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln m2_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln m2_{t-k} + \beta_1 \ln gdp_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln gdp_{t-k} \\ & + \beta_1 \ln inf_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln inf_{t-k} + \beta_1 \ln inv_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln inv_{t-k} \\ & + \beta_1 \ln exc_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln exc_{t-k} + \beta_1 \ln op_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k \ln op_{t-k} \\ & + e \dots\dots\dots (8) \end{aligned}$$

This equation is reflecting the impact of money supply itself and on macro -economic variables (i.e Gross Domestic Product, Inflation, Investment, Exchange rate).

GDP stands for Gross domestic Product (growth rate), m2 is money supply, e stands for error term.

Furthermore, we used Granger causality test, the Granger causality test was first applied by Christopher A. Sims in 1972. This test applied to know granger causal relationship among the variables. Afterwards causal relationship we used the impulse response function, this test is used to identify shock in the system. Impulse response function reveals the dynamic behavior of the vector autoregressive model and it also traces changes in the equations which are shown in the system. It describes the shock in the system. Impulse response function mostly computes forecast of all the variables values in the system during time period and eliminate those values which were not caused of shock (Wieringa & Horváth, 2005).

Forecast error variance can be dependent on the structural innovation and calculations are based on θ_j (Lanne & Nyberg, 2016).

Forecast error variance decomposition is acknowledged of variation in current and future values in the vector auto regressive model (VAR) model. Forecast error variance is based on innovation therefore values of innovation are based on endogenous variables in the VAR model. Each column of variance decomposition value shows in percentage due to its innovation. Each row of variance decomposition adds in 100 (Wai-Ching et al., 2005).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research has applied six variables (i-e Oil Price, Gross Domestic Product, Inflation, Exchange Rate, Money supply, Investment). Unit root tests are applied for achieve the targets of this research. In this regard we have applied two unit root tests i-e augmented dickey fuller and Peron test.

Augmented Dickey Fuller and Philip Peron tests are the most common tests for unit root. Augmented Dickey Fuller test was first introduced by Dicky and Fuller in (1979, 1981). This test is widely suitable for Autoregressive Models; it is used with one period lagged variable and often includes the intercept with time period. This approach detects the Unit Root in data. Another approach is the Philp Perron which also identifies whether the data is either stationary or non-stationary. This was discovered by Philip and Perron in (1988). These both tests results have been shown in table - 1 that indicates that entire macro-variables are integrated I (0). This study has used both tests to clarify the data either it is stationary at the level I (0). These both tests are evident that data of this study does not show any spurious values. The p value of data is identified; the data has no unit root.

Table 1: Unit Root Test

Augmented Dickey Fuller Test			Philip Peron Test	
Variables	At Level	Inference	At Level	Inference
Lnop	-6.141 (0.0000)*	I(0)	-6.294 (0.0000)*	I(0)
Lngdp	-10.418 (0.0000)*	I(0)	-10.320 (0.0000)*	I(0)
Lninf	-23.627 (0.0000)*	I(0)	-22.609 (0.0000)*	I(0)
Lnm2	-5.354 (0.0000)*	I(0)	-5.524 (0.0000)*	I(0)
Lnexc	-9.685 (0.0000)*	I(0)	9.788 (0.0000)*	I(0)
Lnm2	-5.024 (0.0002)*	I(0)	-5.225 (0.0001)*	I(0)

* Indicates probability is < 5%, Lnop = log of oil price, lngdp = log of gross domestic product, lninf = log of inflation, lnexc=log of exchange rate, lnm2 log of money supply.

Another test we have been applied lag length criteria to know the optimal lag of this model, in this table -2 optimal lag length is selected due to lowest value and Akaike Information Criteria is also favored along with other values. This study is selected lag 4 periods due

to the majority of values favored lag 4, AIC lowest value is observed in the period of lag 4.

Table 2: Lag Length Criteri

Lag	LL	LR	FPE	AIC	HQIC	SBIC
0	-5437.13	- -	1.20E+14	49.483	49.5204	49.5755
1	-4991.47	891.32	3.00E+12	45.7588	46.0204*	46.4067*
2	-4969.49	43.953	3.40E+12	45.7588	46.3722	47.0895
3	-4951.71	35.567	4.00E+12	46.0519	46.762	47.8104
4	-4875.69	152.05*	2.8e+12*	45.6881*	46.6225	48.0019

LL= log Likelihood, LR= sequential modified LR test statistics, FPE= final predictor error, AIC = Akaike information criteria, SBIC Schwarz information criteria, HQIC= Hannan Quinn criteria

In table 3, result of this study reveals the oil price has a momentous effect on (i-e Gross domestic product, m2 (Money supply) inflation and on investment). First, third and fourth lag period p values of GDP is significant, whereas the only two lag shows the insignificant. The value of β co-efficient lag period 1, (that is i-e .036799) that shows positive impact on GDP. Whereas t2, t3, t4 (that is i.e -.003821, -.030421, -.051373 respectively) shows the negative impact and t2 is negative and insignificant. Same results are also found by some of economists (Burbidge & Harrison, 2019; Gisser & Goodwin, 2016; Hamilton, 1983; Jiang & Wang, 2011; Tatom, 1988).

First, second and third lag period p value of inflation is insignificant whereas the only one lag shows significant. The value of β co-efficient lag period 4 is (i-e 0.003215) that shows positive impact on inflation. Whereas t1, t2, t3 value (that is i-e 0 .003215, -0.0003001, 0.00179, respectively). First 3 decades, major cause of inflation is political instability in Pakistan, therefore oil price was not cause of increment in inflation that is why oil price first three lag show no response whereas fourth lag results indicated oil price positive impact on inflation because 2007-2008 financial crises are purely related to oil price. Therefore, it escalated inflation. The first period lag p value of investment is significant, whereas second, third and fourth lag period value is insignificant. The value of β co-efficient lag period 1 is (i-e-.015555) that shows negative impact on investment. Whereas t2, t3, t4 value (that is i-e .0059643, -0.004032, 0.04592, respectively).

Table 3: Impact of Oil Price on Macro Variables

VECTOR AUTOREGRESSIVE MODEL						
DEPENDENT VARIABLES	INDEPENDENT VARIABLES					
	Lnop	Ingdp	Ininf	Ininv	Lnexc	Inm2
Lnop (t-1)	[0.727173]	[0.036799]	[0.003215]	[-.015555]	[0.047289]	[-034753]
	0.000	0.000	0.565	0.000	0.625	0.170
	(9.91)*	(5.24)*	(0.57)	(-4.03)*	(0.49)	(-1.37)
Lnop (t-2)	[0.0577897]	[-.003821]	[-.000300]	[.0059643]	[-.048704]	[-0.00228]
	0.528	0.674	0.96	0.245	0.688	0.933
	(0.63)	(0.42)	(0.05)	(1.16)	(-0.40)	(-0.08)

Lnop (t-3)	[-0.018907] 0.836 (0.21)	[-.030421] 0.0001 (3.44)*	[0.001799] 0.763 (0.30)	[-.004032] 0.434 (-0.78)	[0.155761] 0.196 (1.29)	[-031539] 0.907 (-0.12)
Inop (t-4)	[-0.073650] 0.305 (1.03)	[-.051373] 0.000 (7.02)*	[0.011321] 0.040 (2.05)*	[0.004592] 0.244 (1.16)	[-.163925] 0.079 (-1.75)	[-.0081235] 0.749 (-0.32)

➤ Significance level 5%

➤ $t = ()^*$, β co-efficient= [], without brackets represents = p value

Lnop = log of oil price, Lngdp = log of oil gross domestic product Ln = log of inflation, Inexc = log of exchange rate, Lnm2 = log of money supply, Lninv = log of investment

The model stability has been tested before the Impulse Response function and Variance Decomposition (VD). The figure-3 confirmed from the eigenvalues which is evident that the model is stable. All eigenvalues lie under the unit circle. It proves the Vector Autoregressive model is stable.

Figure 3: Unit Root

In this study Impulse Response Functions IRFs generated from the VAR model using the linear specification of crude oil prices. Impulse response function deals with the dynamic impact among the variables. The impulse response function describes the information in signals, and it defined the dynamic shock often it shows dynamic behavior between two variables (Pesavento & Rossi, 2006). In figure 4, the impulse response function and in table 4, variance decomposition results have shown the oil price has given the shock to Pakistan economy. Impulse response function shows in 10 period quarters, Oil price on GDP response reported in period 4th quarter is (5.92144). The positive values in all the period is 0 to 10 quarters. Impulse response trend shows positive response and it moved up to down ward with each respect period. Oil price response on inflation in 5th period is (1.10489) the response of inflation. inflation show positive to negative increasing to

decreasing. (i-e, other factors can be affected on inflation such as political instability, terrorism, increase of import bill of other commodities so that oil price is not sole reason to increase). Oil price response on investment in period 7th quarter is 11.6542. Investment moved toward negative to positive or decreasing to increasing. Oil price shock does not report on Money Supply and Exchange Rate.

Figure 4: Impulse Response Function

Factor Variance Decomposition is proportion of movements in a series due to its own shock and shock of the other variable (Walter Enderson, 2015). The table 4 shows the variation of shock. The variation in GDP is 20 to 24% due to oil price shock (i-e increase of production cost that effect on firms production so that firm reduces output and it is indirectly affected on consumption and investment due to its direct relation with disposable income). The variation in inflation is 3.8% to 4.8% due to oil price shocks (i-e oil price and inflation is indirect relation). The variation in investment is 11 to 12% due to oil price shocks (i-e Oil price decreases investment and more money spends on oil and energy related products). Money supply shows the variation 1 to 6% and exchange rate is 1 to 3% (exchange rate and money supply are affected due to monetary policy).

Table 4: Variance Decomposition

Periods	Inop	Ingdg	Ininf	Ininv	Inexc	Inm2
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0.243711	0.042881	0.128194	0.01635	0.02335
2	0.913739	0.207456	0.040826	0.125279	0.02487	0.015598
3	0.837184	0.208355	0.03922	0.122947	0.030379	0.015474
4	0.750278	0.223142	0.039204	0.120303	0.033369	0.018704
5	0.685692	0.215498	0.038535	0.117355	0.040834	0.02907
6	0.650035	0.217904	0.038304	0.117503	0.048817	0.036365
7	0.628455	0.221788	0.038197	0.122341	0.056737	0.039004
8	0.609381	0.221871	0.038134	0.125386	0.065062	0.039206
9	0.600109	0.220372	0.038193	0.127953	0.068541	0.038749
10	0.592789	0.218514	0.038328	0.128142	0.069403	0.038442

RESEARCH CONTRIBUTION

The study contributes to minimizing the macroeconomic repercussions of shocks of oil price and to achieve economic growth stability in several ways.

First, the research examines the relationship between key macroeconomic variables and impact of the shock of oil price with special focus on the Pakistan economy, which according to my best understanding is very few studies are observed.

- This study provides new evidence on identifying the macroeconomic effects of oil price shock on Pakistan's economy.
- This research employs an empirical methodology that is VAR, and it provides new empirical evidence about the effects of oil price shocks on macroeconomic variables in Pakistan's economy.
- This study covers wider sample quarterly data that is total 245 observations (time period, 1961Q1-2022Q1) thus, the study is one of the comprehensive research work that gives much-needed insight about the movement of key macro-economic variable resulting of price shocks in the oil importing countries, Pakistan.

LIMITATION AND FUTURE RECOMMENDATION

In this research there are few limitations which are given below along with recommendations for future study.

The study inquires about oil price shocks on the macro variables of the economy, macro variables are essential for the economic conditions. This study analyses shocks of oil price on economy so for this reason this study selected macro variables of economy. Moreover, some data variables are not available from 1961 to 2017 (i-e Interest Rate, unemployment). Interest rate and unemployment is a crucial variable for monetary policy, policies are made to keep in mind these factors.

- As per study outcomes, it is recommended that Pakistan should reduce its dependency on crude oil and moves to other sources such as solar, coal, wind and turbines. According to Statistical Review Energy (2021), Pakistan is the 20th largest reserve in the world; therefore it is suggested that Pakistan should speed up the coal energy projects.
- Sindh Punjab and Baluchistan are supposed to be best for solar plants (i,e due to the longer duration of sunny weather) Government should introduce public and private partnership in projects of solar based energy sectors. Industries should also move the electric to solar energy as to fulfill their energy demand.
- Pakistan should also have to work on electric based vehicles, which are very popular in developed countries like Turkey, Japan, and America.
- Pakistan's major oil exporter countries are Saudi Arabia, UAE and Qatar. It is recommended that Pakistan should have to add more exporter countries which could provide the crude oil at the best price.

- Whenever oil price reduces, Pakistan should take quick action to do future contracts with exporter countries and to avail the benefits of reduced oil price.
- This study suggested the future direction of further research that could be impact of oil price on electricity bills in Pakistan.

References

- 1) Ahad, M., & Anwer, Z. (2021). Asymmetric impact of oil price on trade balance in BRICS countries: Multiplier dynamic analysis. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 26(2), 2177-2197.
- 2) Amjad, R., Din, M. U., & Qayyum, A. (2011). *Pakistan: Breaking out of stagflation into sustained growth*.
- 3) Aydın, L., & Acar, M. (2011). Economic impact of oil price shocks on the Turkish economy in the coming decades: A dynamic CGE analysis. *Energy Policy*, 39(3), 1722-1731.
- 4) Basnet, H. C., & Upadhyaya, K. P. (2015). Impact of oil price shocks on output, inflation, and the real exchange rate: Evidence from selected ASEAN countries. *Applied Economics*, 47(29), 3078-3091.
- 5) Bhattacharya, K., & Bhattacharyya, I. (2001). Impact of increase in oil prices on inflation and output in India. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 36(44), 4735-4741.
- 6) Bruno, M., & Sachs, J. (1982). Input price shocks and the slowdown in economic growth: The case of UK manufacturing. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 49(5), 679-705.
- 7) Chen, J., Zhu, X., & Li, H. (2020). The pass-through effects of oil price shocks on China's inflation: A time-varying analysis. *Energy Economics*, 86, 104695.
- 8) Christiano, L. J. (2012). Christopher A. Sims and vector auto regressions. *The Scandinavian Journal of Economics*, 114(4), 1082-1104.
- 9) Cologni, A., & Manera, M. (2008). Oil prices, inflation, and interest rates in a structural cointegrated VAR model for the G-7 countries. *Energy Economics*, 30(3), 856-888.
- 10) Chung, W. H., Tam, H. Y., Wai, P. K. A., & Khandelwal, A. (2005). Time-and wavelength-division multiplexing of FBG sensors using a semiconductor optical amplifier in ring cavity configuration. *IEEE Photonics Technology Letters*, 17(12), 2709-2711.
- 11) Dave, D., & Aye, G. C. (2015). Oil price uncertainty and savings in South Africa. *OPEC Energy Review*, 39(3), 285-297.
- 12) Enders, W. (2015). *Applied econometric time series* (4th ed.).
- 13) Fiza, Q. (2017). The relationship between mutual fund flows and market variables (Doctoral dissertation, University of Malaya).
- 14) Gisser, M., & Goodwin, T. H. (1986). Crude oil and the macroeconomy: Tests of some popular notions: Note. *Journal of Money, Credit and Banking*, 18(1), 95-103.
- 15) Ghosh, S., & Kanjilal, K. (2014). Oil price shocks on the Indian economy: Evidence from Toda Yamamoto and Markov regime-switching VAR. *Macroeconomics and Finance in Emerging Market Economies*, 7(1), 122-139.
- 16) Gong, X., Chen, L., & Lin, B. (2020). Analyzing dynamic impacts of different oil shocks on oil price. *Energy*, 198, 117306.
- 17) Gong, X., Wang, M., & Shao, L. (2022). The impact of macroeconomy on the oil price volatility from the perspective of mixing frequency. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 27(4), 4487-4514.

- 18) Government of Pakistan, F. (2017). *Economic survey of Pakistan*.
- 19) Gujarati, D. N., Porter, D. C., & Gunasekar, S. (2012). *Basic econometrics*. Tata McGraw-Hill Education.
- 20) Hefer, G. (1989). The Cryogenic Ludwieg Tube Tunnel at Göttingen. AGARD, TR, 774.
- 21) Hao, W., Hu, S., & Zhang, H.-W. (2019). Influence factors of international gold futures price volatility. *Transactions of Nonferrous Metals Society of China*, 29(11), 2447-2454.
- 22) Hamilton, J. D. (1983). Oil and the macroeconomy since World War II. *Journal of Political Economy*, 91(2), 228-248.
- 23) Hooker, M. A. (1996). What happened to the oil price-macroeconomy relationship? *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 38(2), 195-213.
- 24) Kamal, M. (2015). Dynamics of natural gas pricing: The critical need for a natural gas hub in South Asia. *Journal of International Affairs*, 69(1), 70-85.
- 25) Kandemir Kocaaslan, O. (2021). Are the responses of output and investment to oil price shocks asymmetric?: The case of an oil-importing small open economy. *Empirical Economics*, 61(5), 2501-2516.
- 26) Khan, M. A., & Ahmed, A. (2011). Macroeconomic effects of global food and oil price shocks to the Pakistan economy: A structural vector autoregressive (SVAR) analysis. *The Pakistan Development Review*, 50(4), 491-511.
- 27) Lee, K., Ni, S., & Ratti, R. A. (1995). Oil shocks and the macroeconomy: The role of price variability. *The Energy Journal*, 16(4), 39-56.
- 28) Lanne, M., & Nyberg, H. (2016). Generalized forecast error variance decomposition for linear and nonlinear multivariate models. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 78(4), 595-603.
- 29) Lardic, S., & Mignon, V. (2006). The impact of oil prices on GDP in European countries: An empirical investigation based on asymmetric cointegration. *Energy Policy*, 34(18), 3910-3915.
- 30) Liu, L. Y., Wang, J. Z., Wei, G. L., Guan, Y. F., Wong, C. S., & Zeng, E. Y. (2012). Sediment records of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in the continental shelf of China: Implications for evolving anthropogenic impacts. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 46(12), 6497-6504.
- 31) Mallick, H. (2009). Examining the linkage between energy consumption and economic growth in India. *The Journal of Developing Areas*, 43, 249-280.
- 32) Månsson, A. (2014). Energy, conflict and war: Towards a conceptual framework. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 4, 106-116.
- 33) Mantai, M. M., & Alom, F. (2016). Impacts of oil price, exchange rate and inflation on the economic activity of Malaysia. *OPEC Energy Review*, 40(2), 180-191.
- 34) Mork, K. A., Olsen, O., & Mysen, H. T. (1994). Macroeconomic responses to oil price increases and decreases in seven OECD countries. *The Energy Journal*, 15(4), 19-35.
- 35) Nasir, M. A., Al-Emadi, A. A., Shahbaz, M., & Hammoudeh, S. (2019). Importance of oil shocks and the GCC macroeconomy: A structural VAR analysis. *Resources Policy*, 61, 166-179.
- 36) Nawab, F., & Ali, S. (2023). The role of oil prices in determining macroeconomic indicators in Pakistan: A cointegration and causality analysis. *Economic Research-Ekonomiska Istraživanja*, 36(1), 2003-2020.
- 37) Oriol, C. (2015). Walter Anderson's letters to Joan Amades: A study of the collaboration between two contemporary folklorists. *Folklore: Electronic Journal of Folklore*, (62), 139-174.

- 38) Prasad, A., Narayan, P. K., & Narayan, J. (2007). Exploring the oil price and real GDP nexus for a small island economy, the Fiji Islands. *Energy Policy*, 35(12), 6506-6513.
- 39) Pesavento, E., & Rossi, B. (2006). Small-sample confidence intervals for multivariate impulse response functions at long horizons. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 21(8), 1135-1155.
- 40) Rasche, R. H., & Tatom, J. A. (1981). Energy price shocks, aggregate supply and monetary policy: The